

Urban Heat Exposure Interactions with Environmental Drivers at the Neighborhood Scale: The Case of Bağcılar and Esenler Districts, Istanbul

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Abstract: Urban heat exposure is an environmental challenge in densely populated metropolitan regions, especially at fine spatial scales where intra-urban thermal disparities arise. This research examines persistent neighborhood-level thermal exposure in two adjacent high-density districts of Istanbul, Bağcılar and Esenler, utilizing Landsat-derived land surface temperature (LST) data from 2016, 2022, and 2024. Environmental drivers of surface temperature were assessed using the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and the Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI), derived consistently for each year. Neighbourhood-level mean LST, NDVI, and NDBI values were calculated using zonal statistics, and multi-year mean values were used to assess the consistency of spatial thermal patterns. Results show that several neighbourhoods in both districts consistently exhibited elevated LST across all three years, indicating spatially persistent thermal hotspots. District-wide mean LST showed interannual variability without a monotonic trend, suggesting spatial heat patterns are more stable than temporal changes. Multiple linear regression identified NDVI as the only significant predictor of LST ($p < 0.05$), with higher explanatory power in Esenler ($R^2 = 0.81$) than in Bağcılar ($R^2 = 0.46$). Regression results indicate that a 0.01 increase in NDVI is associated with an approximately 0.45 °C decrease in LST in Bağcılar and ~0.24 °C in Esenler, while NDBI was not significant. These findings highlight vegetation as the strongest predictor of neighbourhood-scale LST among the variables considered.

Keywords: urban heat exposure; NDVI; NDBI; LST; Istanbul.

1 Introduction

Urban heat islands occur when urban areas exhibit higher temperatures than surrounding rural areas due to land surface modification, reduced vegetation, impervious materials, and anthropogenic heat emissions (Zheng et al. 2026, Anees et al. 2025). Surface urban heat island (SUHI) intensity, derived from satellite-based land surface temperature (LST), enables spatially explicit assessment of intra-urban thermal heterogeneity (Cetin et al. 2024). LST directly reflects land use and land cover transformations associated with urbanization. Spectral indices such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and the Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) are widely used to evaluate vegetation–built environment dynamics and their relationships with LST. Previous research consistently reports negative correlations between NDVI and LST and positive associations between NDBI and LST, highlighting vegetation loss and impervious surface

expansion as key drivers of urban warming (Altınır and Bingöl 2025, Karlınasari et al. 2023). Remote sensing studies in Istanbul have also investigated the relationship between land-cover indices and land surface temperature using Landsat data and correlation analysis (Pashaei and Aksoy 2022). Istanbul, Türkiye’s largest metropolitan area with a population exceeding 15 million, has experienced rapid urban expansion over recent decades (TÜİK 2023, Kuru and Okay 2025). Located in northwestern Türkiye at the interface of Europe and Asia, the city exhibits considerable spatial heterogeneity in land cover and urban morphology. Recent remote sensing analyses demonstrate that continued urban growth and the expansion of impervious surfaces have contributed to increasing land surface temperatures and the intensification of surface urban heat island patterns across the metropolitan region (Kuru and Okay 2025, Karaçam et al. 2026). Recent studies have examined surface urban heat island dynamics in Istanbul at metropolitan, district, and neighborhood scales using multi-temporal remote sensing data (Cigerci et al. 2024, Kuru and Okay 2025, Karaçam et al. 2026). These investigations have identified spatial hotspots and demonstrated significant relationships between urban growth, vegetation loss, and rising land surface temperatures. However, most analyses rely on limited temporal comparisons or metropolitan-scale assessments, and comparatively fewer studies explicitly evaluate the multi-year persistence of neighborhood-level thermal hotspots and quantify the relative statistical influence of vegetation versus built-up intensity on sustained spatial patterns.

This study focuses on the adjacent high-density districts of Bağcılar and Esenler on the European side of Istanbul (Figure 1). Both districts are characterized by compact urban morphology, limited green space, and predominantly built-up land cover. In 2023, Bağcılar had a population of 737,206 and Esenler 454,569 (TÜİK 2023), with Esenler ranking among the most densely populated districts in Istanbul. Previous research identifies these inner-city districts as recurrent thermal hotspots within metropolitan-scale analyses (Cigerci et al. 2024, Zaeemdar and Baycan 2017), and both rank among the lowest districts in Istanbul’s 2020 Quality of Life Index (Şeker et al. 2022), reflecting socio-environmental vulnerability. Their high density, extensive surface sealing, and neighborhood-scale heterogeneity provide a suitable context for evaluating the persistence of urban heat exposure and its environmental determinants. In this study, heat exposure refers to surface thermal conditions derived from satellite-

based LST rather than direct human thermal exposure.

Figure 1. (a) Istanbul Metropolitan Area, (b) Study area: Esenler district with 17 neighborhoods and Bağcılar district with 22 neighborhoods.

Administratively, Bağcılar and Esenler are divided into 22 and 17 neighborhoods, respectively, which constitute the spatial units of analysis in this study. Both districts exhibit high levels of urbanization, with urbanization ratios of 92.5% in Bağcılar and 85.55% in Esenler (Sökmen and Aksoy 2025), indicating predominantly built-up urban fabrics. Bağcılar also has the lowest proportion of green space (8.51%) among highly urbanized districts. Previous studies further characterize Esenler as exhibiting compact morphology, limited vegetation cover, and elevated surface temperatures relative to other districts (Okumuş and Terzi 2021, Dogru et al. 2019).

The objective of this study is to investigate neighborhood-scale urban heat exposure and its environmental drivers in Bağcılar and Esenler using multi-temporal Landsat-derived LST data from 2016, 2022, and 2024. Specifically, the study aims to: (i) identify neighborhoods exhibiting persistently elevated LST across multiple years, (ii) quantify the relationships between LST, NDVI, and NDBI at the neighborhood level, and (iii) assess the relative explanatory power of vegetation and built-up indices in predicting spatial thermal variability using statistical models. By emphasizing neighborhood-level spatial units and multi-year consistency, this research contributes to a more spatially nuanced understanding of urban heat exposure and provides evidence to support targeted heat mitigation strategies.

2 Methodology

Multi-temporal Landsat 8 Collection 2 Level-2 Surface Reflectance and Surface Temperature products were acquired from the USGS Earth Explorer for 7 August 2016, 16 August 2022, and 13 August 2024. All imagery (30 m spatial resolution) was obtained from Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS to ensure inter-annual consistency. All images were acquired during summer conditions under low cloud cover (<10%). The use of images from the same season and

similar acquisition conditions reduces the influence of short-term atmospheric variability, supporting the comparability of spatial LST patterns across years. Neighborhood boundaries were obtained from OpenStreetMap using the QuickOSM plugin in QGIS 3.34.15.

LST was derived from the Level-2 Surface Temperature product (ST_B10) and converted to degrees Celsius using:

$$LST(^{\circ}C) = DN \times 0.00341802 + 149.0) - 273.15 \quad (1)$$

where DN represents the digital number of the thermal band.

Vegetation and built-up intensity were quantified using NDVI and NDBI.

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red} \quad (2)$$

$$NDBI = \frac{SWIR - NIR}{SWIR + NIR} \quad (3)$$

NDVI was calculated using Band 5 (NIR) and Band 4 (Red), while NDBI was derived from Band 6 (SWIR) and Band 5 (NIR).

Administrative neighborhood boundaries were used as spatial analysis units. For each year, mean LST, NDVI, and NDBI values were extracted for each neighborhood using zonal statistical analysis in a QGIS environment. To assess the spatial persistence of thermal exposure, multi-year mean LST values were calculated. Neighborhoods were classified as persistently elevated in temperature based on their consistent ranking within the upper quartile (top 25%) of LST values across all three observation years. Regression models were fitted using multi-year mean neighborhood values (averaged across 2016, 2022, and 2024) rather than year-specific observations, to capture stable spatial relationships.

Pearson correlation and multiple linear regression analyses were conducted to evaluate relationships between LST, NDVI, and NDBI for Bağcılar and Esenler districts:

$$LST_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NDVI_i + \beta_2 NDBI_i + \epsilon_i \quad (4)$$

LST_i represents the mean land surface temperature of the neighborhood i , β_0 is the intercept, β_1 and β_2 are regression coefficients for NDVI and NDBI, respectively, and ϵ_i is the error term.

Model significance was evaluated at the 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$), and explanatory power was assessed using the coefficient of determination (R^2).

3 Results

District-wide mean LST values indicate interannual variability in both Bağcılar and Esenler (Figure 2), with temperatures decreasing in 2022 and increasing again in 2024. In Bağcılar, mean LST declined from 44.54 °C (2016) to 42.60 °C (2022) and rose to 44.71 °C (2024). Esenler showed a similar pattern, decreasing from 44.92 °C to 42.62 °C before increasing to 44.53 °C. These fluctuations suggest short-term atmospheric variability rather than a monotonic warming trend. At the neighborhood scale, LST values remained consistently high in both districts

(Bağcılar: 42.26–45.30 °C, Esenler: 40.41–45.92 °C). Several neighborhoods exhibited persistently elevated temperatures across all years. In Bağcılar, Fatih (B5), Kemalpaşa (B6), and Kazım Karabekir (B18) consistently ranked among the warmest areas. In Esenler, Turgut Reis (E3), Fatih (E10), Namık Kemal (E15), and Kazım Karabekir (E9) displayed sustained thermal intensity. Although moderate local increases and decreases occurred between 2016 and 2024, the overall spatial configuration of higher-temperature neighborhoods remained stable, indicating persistent neighborhood-level heat exposure.

Figure 2. Spatial distribution of LST in Bağcılar and Esenler districts for 2016, 2022, and 2024.

NDVI values were generally low in both districts (Figure 3), reflecting limited vegetation cover and predominantly built-up urban fabric. In Bağcılar, district-wide mean NDVI remained nearly constant (0.07–0.08), with neighborhood values ranging between 0.06 and 0.09. Merkez (B20), Bağlar (B15), Mahmutbey (B1), and Yenimahalle (B10) exhibited comparatively higher vegetation levels, while Kemalpaşa (B6), Fatih (B5), and Yenigün (B22) consistently showed lower NDVI values. In Esenler, mean NDVI ranged from 0.08 to 0.09, with greater intra-district variability. Oruçreis (E1) and Çifte Havuzlar (E17) exhibited comparatively higher NDVI values (≈ 0.17 – 0.18), whereas Turgut Reis (E3), Fatih (E10), and Mimar Sinan (E13) consistently recorded low vegetation levels (≈ 0.05). Overall, vegetation patterns showed limited structural change during the study period.

Figure 3. Spatial distribution of NDVI in Bağcılar and Esenler districts for 2016, 2022, and 2024, illustrating vegetation intensity patterns at the neighborhood level.

NDBI results indicate dense urban development in both districts (Figure 4). In Bağcılar, mean NDBI remained stable at approximately 0.03, while Esenler showed a slight increase from 0.025 to 0.033 between 2016 and 2024. Neighborhoods such as Yenigün (B22) and Yıldıztepe (B21) in Bağcılar and Turgut Reis (E3), Fatih (E10), Mimar Sinan (E13), Nine Hatun (E14), and Kazım Karabekir (E9) in Esenler consistently exhibited higher built-up intensity. Oruçreis (E1) and Çifte Havuzlar (E17) showed negative mean values, consistent with relatively higher vegetation presence. Spatial patterns of built-up land cover remained largely stable, reinforcing the dominance of compact urban morphology.

Figure 4. Spatial distribution of NDBI in Bağcılar and Esenler districts for 2016, 2022, and 2024, representing built-up intensity and urban density patterns

In Bağcılar, Pearson correlation analysis revealed a significant negative relationship between LST and NDVI ($r = -0.68$) and a moderate positive relationship with NDBI ($r = 0.47$). NDVI explained approximately 46% of LST variability, compared to 22% for NDBI. Multiple linear regression was statistically significant ($F = 8.09$, $p = 0.0029$, $R^2 = 0.460$), with NDVI emerging as the only significant predictor ($\beta = -44.89$, $p = 0.009$). A 0.01 increase in NDVI corresponded to an approximate 0.45 °C reduction in LST, whereas NDBI was not statistically significant.

In Esenler, relationships were stronger. LST exhibited a very strong negative correlation with NDVI ($r = -0.89$) and a strong positive correlation with NDBI ($r = 0.85$). The regression model explained 80.7% of spatial LST variability ($F = 29.21$, $p < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.807$). NDVI remained a significant predictor ($\beta = -24.14$, $p = 0.032$), with a 0.01 increase associated with an approximate 0.24 °C decrease in LST. NDBI did not show an independent statistically significant effect. These relationships are illustrated in the scatter plots presented in Figure 5, which show a clear negative slope for NDVI and a positive trend for NDBI in both districts. Overall, results from both districts consistently identify vegetation as the strongest predictor of neighborhood-scale thermal variability among the variables analyzed.

Figure 5. Relationship between mean LST and vegetation and built-up indices in Bağcılar and Esenler districts (2016–2024): (a) LST–NDVI in Bağcılar, (b) LST–NDBI in Bağcılar, (c) LST–NDVI in Esenler, and (d) LST–NDBI in Esenler.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

This study demonstrates that neighborhood-scale thermal exposure in Bağcılar and Esenler is spatially persistent despite interannual atmospheric variability. Although the analysis is based on three summer observations (2016, 2022, and 2024), all acquired under comparable seasonal conditions, the consistent spatial ranking of high-temperature neighborhoods across non-consecutive years supports the interpretation of relative spatial persistence rather than continuous temporal monitoring. Although district-wide mean LST fluctuated between 2016 and 2024, the spatial configuration of high-temperature neighborhoods remained largely stable in both districts, indicating structurally embedded heat patterns rather than short-term climatic effects. These findings complement metropolitan-scale analyses conducted in Istanbul, such as Kuru and Okay (2025) and Karaçam et al. (2026), by demonstrating that thermal persistence is also evident at finer neighborhood scales. Consistent with previous urban heat research (Altınır and Bingöl 2025, Karlınasari et al. 2023), vegetation emerged as the strongest predictor of land surface temperature among the variables analysed. However, this study extends prior findings by revealing district-level differences in explanatory strength. Although both districts are characterized by dense built environments and low mean NDVI values, Esenler exhibited slightly greater vegetation variability and substantially stronger vegetation–temperature relationships ($R^2 = 0.81$) compared to Bağcılar ($R^2 = 0.46$).

These differences likely reflect variations in urban morphology and the spatial configuration of green areas. In Esenler, greater heterogeneity in vegetation distribution appears to enhance localized cooling contrasts, thereby strengthening the statistical relationship with surface temperature. In contrast, Bağcılar’s more homogeneous and consistently low NDVI distribution may limit thermal differentiation across neighborhoods, reducing explanatory power despite an observable cooling effect. The modest increase in mean NDBI observed in Esenler further suggests localized concentrations of built-up intensity that may amplify spatial thermal contrasts. Nevertheless, built-up intensity did not retain independent

significance when vegetation was controlled for, indicating that, at the neighborhood scale, the presence and spatial distribution of green cover outweigh incremental differences in impervious surface intensity.

The persistence of multi-year thermal hotspots reinforces the need for spatially targeted greening interventions rather than generalized district-wide strategies. Even modest increases in vegetation cover may yield measurable cooling benefits, particularly in structurally heterogeneous districts. Overall, this study demonstrates that vegetation-driven cooling is context-dependent and shaped by intra-district spatial structure, highlighting the importance of neighborhood-level green infrastructure in compact metropolitan environments.

5 References

- Altınır, F., Bingöl, F., 2025. Spatio-temporal assessment of land surface temperature, vegetation cover, and built-up areas using LST, NDVI, and NDBI in Balıkesir, Türkiye (1985–2025). *Sustainability* 17 (20), 9245.
- Anees, S.A., Mehmood, K., Raza, S.I.H., Pfautsch, S., Shah, M., Jamjareegulgarn, P., Dube, T., 2025. Spatiotemporal analysis of surface urban heat island intensity and the role of vegetation in six major Pakistani cities. *Ecological Informatics* 85, 102986.
- Cetin, M., Ozenen Kavlak, M., Senyel Kurkcuoglu, M.A., Bilge Ozturk, G., Cabuk, S.N., Cabuk, A., 2024. Determination of land surface temperature and urban heat island effects with remote sensing capabilities: the case of Kayseri, Türkiye. *Natural Hazards* 120 (6), 5509–5536.
- Cigerci, H., Balçık, F. B., Sekertekin, A., Kahya, C., 2024. Unveiling Istanbul’s city dynamics: Spatiotemporal hotspot analysis of vegetation, settlement, and surface urban heat islands. *Sustainability*, 16(14), 5981.
- Dogru, A. O., Kahraman, A., Seker, D. Z., Sivri, N., 2019. GIS based evaluation of social determinants of children’s health in Turkey: Case study of Istanbul. *Environmental research*, 179, 108753.
- Karaçam, M., Kabadayı, E.M., Akar, F.I., Hong, X., Orak, N.H., 2026. Spatial and temporal patterns of daytime surface urban heat islands in Istanbul, Türkiye: insights from a decade of Google Earth Engine analysis. *Mediterranean Geoscience Reviews*, 1–16.
- Karlınasari, L., Pertiwi, S., Erizal, 2023. Urban heat island index change detection based on land surface temperature, normalized difference vegetation index, normalized difference built-up index: a case study. *Journal of Ecological Engineering* 24 (11), 91–107.
- Kuru, A., Okay, B.B., 2025. Investigating the relationship between urban growth pattern and urban heat islands: the case of Istanbul, Turkey. *Environmental Earth Sciences* 84 (1), 43.
- Okumuş, D. E., Terzi, F., 2021. Evaluating the role of urban fabric on surface urban heat island: the case of Istanbul. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 73, 103128.
- Pashaei, M.H., Aksoy, T., 2022. Determining the effect of spatial and temporary change of land cover on land surface temperature using remote sensing aid: the case of Istanbul Pendik district. *GSI Journals Serie C*:

- Advancements in Information Sciences and Technologies 5 (2), 1–22.
- Şeker, M., Baypınar, M. B., Çelikbıçak, G., Özbay, B. K., 2022. Quality of life index: Istanbul 2020. *İstanbul İktisat Dergisi*, 72(2), 543-568.
- Sökmen, E.D., Aksoy, O., 2025. Evaluation of climate justice in open green spaces based on landscape metrics: the case of Istanbul. *Urban Ecosystems* 28 (4), 156.
- Turkish Statistical Institute (TÜİK), 2023. Address-based population registration system (ADNKS) results by neighborhood. <https://data.tuik.gov.tr> (Accessed 1 March 2026).
- Zaeemdar, S., Baycan, T., 2017. Analysis of the relationship between Urban Heat Island and land cover in Istanbul through Landsat 8 OLI. *Journal of Earth Science & Climatic Change*, 8(11), 1000423.
- Zheng, Z., Fong, C.S., Aghamohammadi, N., Law, Y.K., 2026. A systematic review of urban heat island (UHI) impacts and mitigation: health, equity, and policy. *Systems* 14 (1), 82.